

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE RELATION OF THE POLICY OF THE AUTHORITARIAN REGIME TO RELIGION AND SPIRITUAL CULTURE IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

Sagindikov B.
(PhD) doctorate of NSPI
Nukus. Karakalpakstan

Abstract

The article describes the attitude of the Soviet authorities to religion in Karakalpakstan under the influence of the "cultural revolution", the suppression of religious scholars, teachers, and mullahs, and the destruction of old manuscripts, works, and the closing of mosques and madrasas as a result of their influence on spiritual culture.

Keywords: ideology, anti-religion propaganda, cultural revolution, islam, eshon, mullahs, maqsum.

Introduction. In the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, the communist party's policy tried to erase our national culture, religion and values, formed over centuries, from our history as remains of the past, and to instill the advantages of the new Soviet system into the minds and psyche of the people under the policy of false communist ideology.

The ideology of the newly formed political system was based on the Marxist-Leninist ideology in order to centralize the empire. Therefore, the culture of the nations dependent on the empire became of secondary importance. With the establishment of the imperial regime, the ideological direction of anti-religion propaganda and propaganda work were established in April 1923 in the resolution of the XII sezd of the RKP (b): "O postanovke antireligioznoy agitatsii i propagandy" [1] "Intensification of anti-religion propaganda and propaganda work" drew attention to the issue. From this moment on, new main directions of propaganda work in the field of education and enlightenment began to be formed.

The purpose of the cultural revolution under the leadership of the Bolshevik Party is to look at the issue of culture from the point of view of the class struggle and to inculcate its ideas through pressure on the national territories, supporting the international culture of the nations rather than their own national culture.

Attitude against religion. The October coup of 1917 in Russia, the emergence of the new Soviet system "It set the norms of class struggle aimed at establishing proletarian culture" in the national territories dependent on it. Namely: in Russia itself, the measures of "separation of the church from the state and the state from the church" [2] opened the way to the strengthening of anti-religious propaganda among the people, and the liberation of culture from the influence of the church. Here the question arises: what kind of culture can be far from its religion, program and national mentality?

From the first day of the establishment of the Soviet power, as a result of the Russian and other Europeans taking power in the Amudarya region, they did not raise any issues about the restoration of the national statehood of the Karakalpak people during the years 1917-1924. During these years, most of the enlighteners and intellectuals were religious scholars with old literacy. For example, the deputies of the Muslim council

in the country expressed a negative reaction to the transfer of power to the Soviets.

About the will and goals of the local people, Abdulla Rahimbaev, one of the famous public figures of Turkestan, expressed the following honest opinion about the attitude of the local people to the "Revolution and the attempt to build a socialist society carried out by the Bolsheviks": "The Muslim population was afraid of any innovation, the socialist revolution principles were incomprehensible to them, because they originated from the European part of the population, and were suspicious" [3], as he noted, the same situation happened in the territory of Karakalpakstan.

On May 23, 1918, on the instructions of the Soviet of People's Commissars of the Turkestan ASSR, the Soviet of the Amudarya region issued an order to separate the church from the state. This order caused some dissatisfaction of the population. The revolutionary committee persecuted and imprisoned those who resisted [4]. As a result, the new imperial system carried out intimidation and various policies among the local population, and with the help of the poor, separated the school from the church.

Against the policy of the Soviet government, popular religious scholars with old literacy among the people, and the aggressors protested.

On July 29, 1919, an armed uprising began, in which 17 commissars of the Amudarya region were killed. The rebels formed a people's government under the leadership of Ubaydulla Bawetdinov, which included Ibrahim Adilov, Iniyat Niyazov, Seytnazar Pirnazarov, Qutlimurat Tajimuratov, and ataman Mikhail Filchev. But soon the uprising was suppressed [6].

On January 24, 1920, upon the arrival of Ataman Filchev from Guryev, a detachment of 300 Kazakhs and 400 Karakalpaks under the command of Khan Maqsum, armed with 2 cannons and 4 machine guns, attacked Nukus and Khodzheyli. The Soviet garrison left by N. A. Shaydakov in Nukus gave them a fierce blow. The Khodzheyli garrison consisting of 140 people resisted for 3 days [7].

As soon as Khan Maqsum and Filchevs agreement with the Soviet armed forces and supporters of the coup came under discussion, representatives of the local population began to participate in state organizations. However, in February 1921, 24 active participants of

the uprisings in Chimboy district were arrested and exiled. Famous people like Eshon Karakum were deprived of the right to participate in council elections. As for Khan Maqsum, he was exiled to Siberia [8].

In April 1920, the Khiva Khanate was overthrown and replaced by the Khorezm People's Soviet Republic (KPSR). In the middle of this year, the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic (BPSR) was established instead of the Bukhara Emirate. These events also affected the people of Karakalpakstan. Especially the actions of the Uzbek, Turkmen, Tajik, Kyrgyz, Kazakh peoples living in Central Asia in order to restore their national statehood in 1924, called "National Boundation" and their achievement of their goals encouraged the people of Karakalpak with the realization of their dreams [9].

On October 14, 1924, the Central Executive Committee of the Former Union Council approved the decision on the establishment of the Karakalpakstan Autonomous Region, which was part of the Autonomous Republic of Kazakhstan within the RSFSR. On February 12-19, 1925, the first constituent assembly of the Karakalpakstan Autonomous Region, held in Turtkul, announced the "Declaration on the Establishment of the Karakalpakstan Autonomous Region" legally confirmed the restoration of the citizen and their incorporation into the Kazakhstan ASSR [10].

During the restoration of Soviet power in Karakalpakstan and the establishment of the Autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan, supporters of the constitutional monarchy tried to achieve national independence through constitutional means, the protests of the religiously educated groups who tried to implement national independence through reforms and did not approve of the coup did not stop suddenly against the education policy of the Soviet government. On August 22, 1924, in the "Begjab" area, on the left bank of the Amudarya, 30 km north of the city of Khodzheyli, Durdi Qilich Khan's raiders, consisting of 100 cavalymen, stopped a ship traveling along the river and killed 22 unarmed young cadets who were going to study from Khorezm to Tashkent, Almaty and Moscow [11].

Since the second half of the 1920s, the representatives of religion were severely persecuted and most of them were repressed. Mosques were closed. Although Islam does not prevent women from participating in social life and production, a policy of non-recognition of Islam was carried out. This, in turn, increased the hostility towards the Soviet government among the local population [12].

With this mood, the population tried to preserve the age-old rules. Due to their low worldview, they did not understand that they could not defeat the regime backed by the Red Army with their own terrorist actions, so they killed the servants of the Soviet regime, who were their fellow villagers. These actions of theirs were actions that did not correspond to the rules of Islam – shedding innocent blood, leaving the children of people like themselves as orphans. ... Basically, in 1925, the Soviet government, with the establishment of the "Union of Battle Atheists" [13], this organization together with the Department of People's Commissars of Internal Affairs slandered most of the religious

scholars and old literate intellectuals with various baseless accusations, and most of them were expelled.

Attitude towards religious schools. Despite the preservation of the historical heritage of the people of Central Asia in the fields of religion, science and culture, which contributed to the world civilization during the ancient and medieval times, the colonial system tried to establish its ideology of sole governance. In order to do this, he established new Soviet educational institutions that served to establish his ideology. In 1918, the Socialist Academy was opened.

From 1919 The Communist University named after Ya. M. Sverdlov was transformed into a center for training ideological and ideological personnel. As a result, from 1919 to 1926, 20 volumes of the works of Soviet geniuses were published [5]. This situation laid the foundation for the all-round development of the propaganda work of the imperial system.

Despite the intensification of anti-religious propaganda in Karakalpakstan, in the second half of the 20s, mosques-madrasas continued their effective activity among the population. For example, in the 1926-1927 academic year, 76 religious schools served in the Turtkul region, and 1098 people were educated in them [14]. At the beginning of 1927, there were 25 religious schools in Chimboy Volost, where 270 people studied [15].

However, due to the fact that these educational institutions did not have special buildings and were not provided with the textbooks in demand of the time, the reputation of religious schools began to decline as a result of the propaganda work of the organizations that absorbed the politics of the Soviet system.

Nevertheless, the new Soviet system implemented its policy and purpose. In 1929-1930, the funds allocated for school construction increased by 20 percent compared to 1926-1927. New schools in rural areas were named "White House – "Beliy Dom". The rich and clergy fought against the implementation of the culture of the Soviet system in rural areas and destroyed school buildings [16].

According to Doctor of History science Ya. M. Dosumov, if it is confirmed that "confessional schools in Karakalpakstan functioned until 1927" [17], in his research, M. Karlibaev shows that in all regions of Karakalpakstan, mosques and madrasahs ceased to exist since 1928 [18]. Ismetulla Eshon madrasa was located on the territory of Qasim Awezov peasant farm in Chimboy district, his son Ismetullaev Abduljamil was persecuted in 1929 for participating in "propaganda activities against the Soviet government" and for being a descendant of a religious scholar [19].

On September 7, 1929, the issue "About Muslim schools of the old method" was discussed and a decision was made in the bureau of the regional party committee of Karakalpakstan. "Since the religious schools work together under the mosques, the implementation of the decision of the regional committee bureau to temporarily close the religious schools was temporarily delayed" [20].

Therefore, the completion of the old method schools was postponed not to 1927, but to the 1929-

1930 academic year. The complete abolition of confessional schools led to the full implementation of the decree of the Soviet government on the separation of the church from the state and the school from the church, that is, the destruction of the old foundations and the creation of a single state system of Soviet schools in Karakalpakstan. Secondly, this period included the implementation of the "Regulations of the unified labor school of Kazakhstan ASSR" [21] approved by Kazsovnarkom.

During the period of political consolidation of the Soviet system, the services of the departments of the "Organization of Struggle Gods" were further strengthened, and in their propaganda work, they explained that "the rules of the Muslim religion are designed for the interests of the representatives of the ruling class" [22].

The documents of the Oblast Party Committee related to the year 1928 related to the strengthening of atheist propaganda against religious believers in the territory of Karakalpakstan contain the following information: "The influence of the priests among the people is strong, as a result of their propaganda, thousands of worshipers come to the cemeteries, mainly for religious pilgrimages such as "Sultan Baba" and "Narinjan Baba", and bring money, goods, and food to the cemeteries" [23], – was written like this. Here, we must make it clear that in all nations of the world, visiting one's deceased ancestors, deceased parents, or close relatives is not worshiping or begging God. Despite this, we can see that in these years, under the guise of religion, people were forbidden to visit cemeteries during atheistic propaganda and education.

During the struggle against religion, the Soviet regime interfered with women's rights, and had an impact on the violation of the programmatic mentality of Eastern women who considered their family and child-rearing as sacred.

However, the transformation of wealthy businessmen and old literate priests into enemies of their country and enemies of the people caused great damage to the gene pool and morale of our people. They had a negative impact on the lives of their sons and daughters in their families. They called them sons or daughters of the enemy and people did not allow them to join to their side and even to study.

In the history of the people of the East and Central Asia, for more than a thousand years, the religion of Islam has been a source of education that leads a person to spiritual maturity, faith and kindness. However, we should support the opinion of professor Tajen Izimbetov, saying that it would be wrong to overestimate the role of the "Union of Fighting Atheists" in the 1920s and its impact on propaganda in the fight against religion [24]. Because since the establishment of the new public system, the Soviet authorities have recruited propagandist cadres from the local population who did not have sufficient knowledge in the course of their open struggle against Islam, using them for nefarious purposes, making families who had been living in harmony hostile to each other.

Attitude towards spiritual culture. In the anti-religion propaganda of the Bolshevik Party, under the

pretext of forming a scientific outlook on the world in the minds of the representatives of the local nation, they strengthened the struggle to form an anti-religion point of view and realized the goal of changing the socio-political and spiritual culture of the people from the original roots.

The direct pressure of the policy of the ruling regime on the religion and spiritual culture of the Karakalpak people was not only to banish the religious people, but also to destroy our written sources, which contributed to the world civilization during the early renaissance of the East.

The peoples of Central Asia were educated in the mosque madrasas, which were useful from the written sources of the Eastern greats, and our ancestors used the Arabic alphabet for more than a thousand years. Of course, this writing had its own difficulties. During the establishment of the Soviet system in Karakalpakstan, it was aimed to switch to the new Latin alphabet in order to prohibit the use of sources in the developed Arabic script characteristic of Islamic religious culture. Manuscripts and books in Arabic writing were burned, causing irreparable losses to our spiritual culture.

From the mid-1920s, the propagandists of the new regime launched a massive attack against the Arabic script in the Karakalpakstan press, educational institutions, red houses, teahouses, theater stages, and later on radio broadcasts, as well as from the pulpits of public gatherings. No other writing in history has been attacked with such ferocity. The writing of the Arabic alphabet was declared to be the cause of all our backwardness, illiteracy, and religiosity [25]. As a result of the transition to the Latin alphabet from the 1929-1930 academic year, we abandoned the scientific, spiritual and philosophical written sources of the Arabic script of the early renaissance period of the Turkic-speaking peoples.

The project of the first Latinized Karakalpak alphabet was established by Q. Awezov, S. Majitov and others. And it was recommended to the committee of Karakalpakstan Autonomous Region on July 30, 1928. At the end of 1928, the new Latinized Karakalpak alphabet was adopted with several changes [26].

Attitude towards literature. The Soviet government forcibly introduced its ideological vices against Karakalpak folk literature, which had been developing on the basis of national literary programs for centuries. They came up with a method of false socialist realism, which promotes a socialist way of life and support for party politics, which is incompatible with the public political and social life of the people. Thus, a multi-national Soviet literature appeared, which could not leave the lines drawn by the Soviet government and the party, "national in form, socialist in content", and as time passed, this process began to spread widely.

The ideology of the Bolshevik party set poets as the main task of writing about the victory of the October Revolution, the superiority of Soviet power, the policy of the Communist Party, the image and life of the new Soviet people who are loyal to the great ideas of the genius, the brotherhood and friendship of the peoples among the nations, the powerful socialist

state system, the example of the collective farm villages, the happy and free life of the people and the education of the people in the communist spirit as well as many other political topics

Writers and poets were directed to promote the Soviet regime. However, these poets still did not know enough about the politics of the new government, how it differs from the previous era. At that time, propagandists and agitators appeared. Their instruction, that is, at the request of the party, slogans and definitions, poems came to the square such as “Enter the collective farm”, “Unify as an artef”, “Comrades”, “Ilya’s son”. These were works that had no future and were created depending on the demand of the time [27].

Conclusion. In conclusion, we can see that the attitude of the totalitarian regime to religion and spiritual culture was carried out under the instructions of the Bolshevik Party, which was in control of the state administration. Through illegal decrees, they parted with the religious values of our people, which are the treasure of morality, kindness, purity and faith.

Secondly, the written sources in Arabic and Persian languages, which contributed to the world civilization of the people of Central Asia with more than a thousand years of history, were destroyed.

Thirdly, the local religious priests who contributed to the development of our spiritual culture were persecuted, and the sacred places that served our people were destroyed.

Fourthly, examples of European culture and literature, which are not characteristic of our national mentality, began to enter. Despite this, cultural achievements formed on the basis of the new system in the fields of education, science, and medicine were highlighted.

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ПЕРВАЯ МИРОВАЯ ВОЙНА И ЕЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ТУРКЕСТАН

Дорошенко Т.И.

*Кандидат исторических наук, доцент
Национальный университет Узбекистана
Узбекистан, Ташкент*

THE FIRST WORLD WAR AND ITS IMPACT ON TURKESTAN

Doroshenko T.

*Candidate of Historical Sciences, Associate Professor
National University of Uzbekistan
Uzbekistan, Tashkent*

Аннотация

Статья посвящена влиянию Первой мировой войны на Туркестан. Уже с сентября 1914 года в край стали прибывать сначала военнопленные Австро-венгерской и Германской армий, а затем интернированные и беженцы. Это коренным образом повлияло и изменило жизнь коренного и европейского населения Туркестана. Во многих городах число прибывших превышало численность коренного населения, что беспокоило местную администрацию. Ухудшилась жилищная ситуация и продовольственное снабжение. В статье показано отношения царской и местной администрации Туркестана к военнопленным и беженцам разных национальностей. К военнопленным неприятельских государств отношение было жестче, они использовались на тяжелых работах, в шахтах, на строительстве, на железной дороге и др., к представителям славянских национальностей, как в России, так и в Туркестане относились более лояльно.

Цель статьи состоит в том, чтобы воссоздать целостную картину положения беженцев и военнопленных Первой мировой войны в Туркестане, показать трансформацию положения военнопленных и беженцев в 1914-1918 гг.

Объектом исследования стали вынужденные мигранты Первой мировой войны, а именно: беженцы, интернированные и военнопленные, оказавшиеся в Туркестане.

Актуальность проблемы связана, в первую очередь, с тем, что к настоящему времени проблема миграций в целом, беженства, в частности, обострилась. В XXI в., когда военные конфликты, как и прежде, являются одной из форм межгосударственных и межнациональных отношений, все сопутствующие им проблемы сохраняют свою актуальность.

Abstract

The article is devoted to the impact of the First World War on Turkestan. Already in September 1914, prisoners of war of the Austro-Hungarian and German armies began to arrive in the region, and then internees and refugees. This radically influenced and changed the life of the indigenous and European population of Turkestan. In many cities, the number of arrivals exceeded the number of indigenous people, which worried the local administration. The housing situation and food supply have deteriorated. The article also shows the attitude of the tsarist and local administration of Turkestan to prisoners of war and refugees of different nationalities. The attitude towards the prisoners of war of the enemy states was harsher, they were used in heavy work, in mines, construction, on the railway, etc., representatives of Slavic nationalities, both in Russia and in Turkestan, were treated more loyally. The purpose of the article is to recreate a holistic picture of the situation of refugees and prisoners of war of the First World War in Turkestan, to show the transformation of the situation of prisoners of war and refugees in 1914-1918. The object of the study was forced migrants of the First World War, namely: refugees, internees and prisoners of war who ended up in Turkestan. The urgency of the problem is primarily due to the fact that by now the problem of migration in general, and refugees in particular, has worsened. In the XXI century, when military conflicts, as before, are one of the forms of interstate and interethnic relations, all the problems accompanying them remain relevant.

Ключевые слова: Первая мировая война, Туркестан, военнопленные, интернированные, беженцы, национальность.

Keywords: World War I, Turkestan, prisoners of war, internees, refugees, nationality.